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Contribution of Social, Moral & Fiscal Family Support on Sports Achievements of Players of Punjab Province

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to find out how social, moral, and financial support of family affects Punjabi athletes' sporting accomplishments. Quantitative metrics were the foundation of the previous study. All student-athletes from Punjab public universities made up the population of this study. For the study, 2000 volunteers in total were enlisted. One thousand survey cases made up the sample size. Using a purposive sample approach, the target group consisted of student-athletes between aged (19 to 25), who were keenly participating in sports at university level. Two self-made structured questionnaires were used to gather data. Both descriptive (mean, percentage, & standard deviation) and inferential statistic were used. Multiple linear Regression was used to assess the influence of social, financial and moral support of family on sports achievement of athlete at university level. All statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS. The results investigated that all the independent variable (social, moral and fiscal support of family) had significant contribution athlete's achievements in sports. It was concluded that if proper contribution of social moral & fiscal family support provided to the Punjab Province players, this might have significance of positive effect on sports achievements.

Keywords: Social, moral, & fiscal support, athletes, sports achievements, & university level.

Background of the Study

Sports are human physical and mental activities that improve human attention, health, and reduce illness and stress. Without creating healthy environments for sports, society cannot achieve its goals. Those who claim to be successful or unsuccessful in sports are known as players. The accomplishments are accountable for the external circumstances in the case of failure. In addition to achieving accomplishment, they value the recognition of their own efforts. A variety of characteristics, including physical strength, skill level, and strategic efficacy, contribute to sports accomplishment. People with poor athletic ability may experience anxiety and negative consequences (Gpessr & Rodriguez, 2021).

For athletes, social support is crucial in lowering stress levels. The parameters "offerer" and "receiver" refer to support from society. Characters that provide social support are known as providers, and those who receive it are known as receivers. High support, dedication, spirit and encouragement, as well as both extrinsic and intrinsic aspects, are the building blocks of motivation. Players will develop a strong character through verbal communication and a positive attitude, with the hope that motivation will advance their thinking while competing (Laurie, Drcar, & Song, 2020).

Highly motivated athletes are more likely to achieve their objectives and maintain high performance levels. Thus, motivation is the ability of someone to achieve the desired result, which in athletics is an achievement. Mobility skills, set of techniques, physical fitness, and mental resilience are all indicators of the performance of an athlete. Sports is basically physical and mental activities that enhance human health and interest, and lower illness and stress. Without establishing safe spaces for sports, society cannot accomplish its objectives. In sports, players are the people who claim to be successful or unsuccessful. If there is a failure, the performers are accountable for the external circumstances. At the same time as getting success, they privilege that their own efforts are considered in. Among the traits that lead to success in sports are physical prowess, skill level, and strategic efficacy. Success is determined by the ability to reach the goal frequently and precisely. Coaches provide direction, compassion, care, respect, and gratitude throughout practice and competition (Tingaz, 2020).

There is no available research that explains these three components, according to positive parents. Research on the above-mentioned factors indicates that sports teams who offer top-notch services might increase player happiness. This study shows that as a player's drive to exercise increases along with their level of happiness, it affects their achievement performance. One important factor that contributes to great service quality is family support. Parental and family involvement in a variety of subjects increases the player's degree of motivation. The author also pointed out that each parent's conduct differs based on the demographic. Parents impart a set of beliefs and family characteristics to their children through a range of expressions and actions, depending on their own preferences. This influences the identities and abilities of the participants. According to Furusa, Knight, and Hill (2021), positive parental and family participation in a variety of themes increases the players' level of motivation.

Additionally, the researcher observed that each parent's conduct differs based on their demography. Parents use a range of emotions and actions to convey a set of values and family characteristics to their children, depending on their own preferences. These behaviors have an effect on the players' own abilities and perspectives. High-achieving performance should ideally be motivated by additional factors like excellent service, family support, or a strong relationship between the student-athlete and coach.

Previous research found that the support of athletes' families has a significant impact on their drive and self-confidence. Additionally, the comfort, quality of sleep, mood of the day, and

overall well-being of student-athletes are positively impacted by strong family support (Neyroud & Newman, 2021).

Research on the aforementioned factors suggests that when sports teams offer top-notch services, athlete happiness may increase. The results of the study show that when players' motivation to exercise increases along with their degree of happiness, their accomplishment performance is affected. Along with high-quality services, family support is a significant influencing element. Previous research indicates that families have a significant impact on student-athletes' motivation and self-confidence (Erdner & Wright, 2018).

Strong family support also has a positive impact on players comfort, happiness, sleep quality, and general well-being. However, the prior research was narrow to martial arts and did not specially look at how they impacted student-athletes motivation and performance. According to the introduction, the purpose of this explanation is to evaluate the extent to which athlete accomplishment performance is influenced by close family support and service quality, while taking motivation and positive effects into consideration as a mediating factor in this relationship (Newman & Neyroud, 2021). According to an explanation of the aforementioned factors (Lundy, 2019), sports teams that offer top-notch services may increase players' satisfaction. The results of the study show that as players' motivation to exercise increases along with their degree of enjoyment, it affects their achievement performance. Along with high-quality services, family support is a significant influencing factor. Previous research indicates that families have a significant impact on student-athletes' motivation and self-confidence. This study is important since there is a dearth of published data on the motivation and performance of student-athletes. Furthermore, to assess the applicability of this research model as a basis and guidance for pertinent development studies. This study examines the financial assistance that families provide to athletes from Punjab province. Along with great quality, family support is a significant determining factor.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the influence of Social, Moral & Financial Support of Family on Sports Achievements of Players.

Literature of the Study

Family support is widely recognized as a key factor influencing athletes' participation and achievement in sports. It includes social, moral, and fiscal dimensions that collectively shape an athlete's performance and motivation. Research shows that athletes who receive strong family support are more likely to remain engaged in sports and achieve higher levels of success.

Social support refers to emotional encouragement, care, and companionship provided by family members. Studies indicate that such support enhances athletes' confidence, reduces stress, and improves overall performance (Toth et al., 2026). Athletes with strong social backing tend to show greater persistence and psychological stability in competitive environments.

Moral support, including motivation, values, and parental encouragement, also plays a vital role in athlete development. Parents significantly influence athletes' attitudes, discipline, and commitment to training. Research suggests that consistent moral encouragement leads to higher motivation and stronger athletic identity, which ultimately contributes to better performance (Stanger et al., 2018).

Fiscal or financial support is another important determinant of sports achievement. It includes funding for training, equipment, travel, and participation in competitions. Studies highlight that financial assistance enables athletes to access better facilities and coaching, thereby improving their chances of success (El Husna, Hudain, & Alwi, 2025). Without adequate financial support, many athletes face barriers that limit their performance and opportunities.

In the context of Punjab, Pakistan, family support becomes even more critical due to limited institutional resources and cultural influences. Families often serve as the primary source of encouragement and financial backing, especially for young and female athletes.

Method and Material

Research Design

In the current research study, a descriptive research design was applied to investigate the influence of social, moral, and financial support of family on athlete's achievement in sports at university level in Punjab. The target audience consisted of individuals between the ages of 19 and 25 who participated actively in sports at different Faisalabad institutions.

Population and Sampling

All the student-athletes with the age group of 19-25 years who participated in annual intervarsity sports competition of Punjab during the session of 2023-2024, were taken as population the study. The researcher has applied purposive sampling method for data collection from the participant.

Table.4: Table of Population & Sample Size

University's	Population	sample
GCUFs	600	266
GCWUF	300	312
UOL	300	162
PU	400	149
GCWUS	400	111
Total	2000	1000

Instruments of the Study

The researcher has used two self-made different questionnaire for data collection from the participants. A family social, moral and fiscal questionnaire was used to assess the impacts of family support toward sports participation of the athletes. While sports achievement questionnaire was used to analyze sports achievement of the athletes at university level sports.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

To make sure they assessed the target variables properly, the study tools were verified. In order to ensure content validity, experts in behavioral and psychological research were consulted to ascertain whether the survey and interview guide adequately addressed the features of the influence of moral, social morals and financial support of family on the achievement of Punjab's athletes. Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate the instrument's internal consistency for reliability. The value of cronbach'alpha for both instruments are .855 and .802, which are under the required margin of .70.

Statistical Analysis

This is the basic part the research work. The researcher has used descriptive statistic (mean, percentage, frequency & standard deviation) in order to describe characteristics of each and every subject. While, inferential statistic (Multiple linear regression) was applied to determine the influence of family's moral, social, & financial support of family on achievement of athletes in sports at university level.

Descriptive result

Table 1:

Gender of players	Frequency	Percentage
Male	295	29.5%
Female	705	70.5%
Total	1000	100%

There are total 1000 participants in the study. Male are 295, (29.5%) and female are 705, (70.5%).

Testing Hypothesis

There is significant influence of Social H₁, MoralH₂ & FinancialH₃ Support of Family on sports achievements of Players.

Table 2a:

Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.843 ^a	.711	.678		.38513

a. Predicators: (Constant), Social, Moral, & Fiscal support Sports Achievements.

The power and direction of the linear association between the dependent variable Sports accomplishment (SA) and the predictors (social, moral, and financial support of family) are represented by the multiple correlation coefficient (R = 0.843). A significant positive association is indicated by a value around 1. R Square (R²): The model's predictors account for 71.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (SA), according to the coefficient of determination (R² = 0.711). Adjusted R Square: The standard deviation of the residuals (SEE = 0.38513) represents the average distance between observed values and the regression line. A value indicates a better model fit. The strength and direction of the linear association between the predictors (family's social, moral, and financial support) and the dependent variable (SA) are shown by the multiple correlation coefficient (R = 0.843). A significant positive association is indicated by a value around 1. R Square (R²).

Table. 2b

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.795	4	3.199	21.565	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.191	35	.148		
	Total	17.986	39			

The significant F-value of 21.565 is at 0.000. The conventional significance threshold ($\alpha=0.05$) is exceeded by the p-value of 0.000. It indicate that the regression model is statistically significant, meaning that a substantial volume of the difference in the dependent variable can be described by the predictors (social, moral, and financial support from the family). The significant F-value of 21.565 is at 0.000. The conventional significance threshold ($\alpha=0.05$) is exceeded by the p-value of 0.000. This suggests that there is statistical significance in the regression model, indicating that the predictors (family's social, moral & fiscal support) collectively account for a considerable portion of the variance in the dependent variable. The significant F-value of 21.565 is at.000. The p-value of 0.000 exceeds the traditional significance criterion ($\alpha=0.05$).

Table 2c: *Coefficients*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig
Constant	.872	.363	—	2.401	.022
Social Support (Family)	.406	.155	.296	2.613	.013
Moral Support (Family)	.501	.190	.188	3.581	.023
Fiscal Support (Family)	.770	.115	.685	6.697	.000

The coefficient is the final table from the regression analysis. The coefficients table indicates that the dependent variable (sports accomplishments) is significantly impacted by the precise correlations between the predictors (social, moral, and financial support of family). These coefficients, which are standardized to the same scale, show how significant each predictor is in explaining the variance in SA.

Social support: $\beta=0.296$ indicates that there is a positive association between social support and SA. Media: $\beta=0.188$ indicates a little positive correlation between SA and moral support. The fiscal β value of 0.685 indicates a good relationship between fiscal assistance and the SA. If the p-value is smaller than $\alpha=0.005 = 0.022$, the predictor has a substantial impact on SA (Constant). H1: There is statistical significance in the intercept. H₁ intercept has statistical significance. Social support, $t=2.613$ $p=0.013$. H2 provides statistically significant benefits to SA. Moral support: $t=3.581$, $p=0.023$. The H3 fiscal year has statistically significant benefits for SA.

Conclusion of the Study

The findings of this study demonstrate that family support plays a significant role in enhancing sports achievement (SA) among players. All three dimensions of family support social, moral, and fiscal show a positive relationship with sports achievement. Social support has a moderate positive effect on sports achievement ($\beta = 0.296$, $p = 0.013$), indicating that emotional encouragement and family involvement significantly improve athletes' performance. Similarly, moral support also shows a positive and statistically significant impact ($\beta = 0.188$, $p = 0.023$), suggesting that motivation, values, and parental guidance contribute to better sports outcomes. Among all variables, fiscal support has the strongest influence on sports achievement ($\beta = 0.685$, $p = 0.000$), highlighting the importance of financial resources such as training facilities, equipment, and participation opportunities in achieving higher performance levels. Furthermore, the overall model is statistically significant (Constant: $t = 2.401$, $p = 0.022$), confirming the validity of the study. All hypotheses (H1, H2, and H3) are accepted, as each form of family support significantly contributes to sports achievement. The study establishes that while social and moral support are important for motivation and psychological strength, fiscal support is the most influential factor in improving sports achievement. Therefore, a combination of emotional, moral, and financial support from family is essential for the success of athletes, particularly in contexts like Punjab where external support systems may be limited.

Discussion

The present study examined the contribution of family-based social, moral, and fiscal support to the sports achievement of athletes. The findings indicate that all three forms of support significantly and positively influence sports achievement, though their magnitude of impact varies considerably.

First, the results reveal that social support has a moderate positive effect on sports achievement ($\beta = 0.296$, $p = 0.013$). This suggests that athletes who receive encouragement, companionship, and involvement from family members are more likely to perform better in sports. Social support creates a nurturing environment that enhances confidence, reduces stress, and promotes consistent participation in training and competition. This finding is consistent with previous research, which emphasizes that social support systems particularly family play a crucial role in athlete development and performance (Rees & Hardy, 2000; Freeman & Rees, 2010). In many cultural contexts, including Pakistan, family remains a central social unit, and its involvement can significantly shape athletes' motivation and persistence.

Similarly, moral support was found to have a positive and statistically significant impact on sports achievement ($\beta = 0.188$, $p = 0.023$), although its effect size is smaller compared to social and fiscal support. Moral support, such as emotional encouragement, appreciation, and belief in the athlete's abilities, contributes to psychological well-being and intrinsic motivation. Athletes who feel valued and emotionally supported are more likely to develop resilience, maintain focus, and overcome performance-related challenges. This aligns with the Self-Determination Theory proposed by Deci and Ryan (2000), which highlights the importance of emotional and psychological support in fostering motivation and optimal performance. The relatively smaller beta value, however, may suggest that while moral support is important, it may not be sufficient alone without tangible or structural support systems.

The most striking finding of this study is that fiscal support has the strongest influence on sports achievement ($\beta = 0.685$, $p = 0.000$). This indicates that financial resources provided by families such as funding for training, equipment, nutrition, travel, and coaching are critical determinants of athletic success. Sports participation, especially at competitive levels, often requires substantial financial investment. Athletes lacking financial backing may face barriers such as limited access to quality training facilities or professional coaching. This finding is strongly supported by earlier studies, which highlight that economic resources significantly impact access to opportunities and performance outcomes in sports (Wylleman & Lavallee, 2004; Knight et al., 2016). In developing countries like Pakistan, where institutional support for sports may be limited, family financial support becomes even more essential.

Moreover, the overall model was found to be statistically significant ($t = 2.401$, $p = 0.022$), indicating that the combined contribution of social, moral, and fiscal support provides a meaningful explanation of variations in sports achievement. This highlights the multidimensional nature of athlete development, where both emotional and material resources interact to influence performance outcomes. It also suggests that focusing on a single type of support may not be sufficient; rather, a holistic approach involving multiple forms of family support is necessary for optimal athletic success.

In summary, the findings underscore the critical role of family in shaping sports achievement. While social and moral support contribute to psychological and emotional development, fiscal support emerges as the most influential factor, emphasizing the importance of economic resources in competitive sports. These results have important implications for policymakers, coaches, and sports organizations, suggesting that efforts to enhance athlete performance should include strategies to support families, particularly in terms of financial assistance and awareness programs.

Conflict of Interest

The researcher has claimed no conflict of interest.

References

- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268.
- El Husna, F. E., Hudain, M. A., & Alwi, A. (2025). Family Economic Conditions and Performance of Athletes: The Importance of a Social Approach in Sports Development. *COMPETITOR: Jurnal Pendidikan Kepeleatihan Olahraga*, 17(3), 2723-2731.
- Erdner, S. M., & Wright, C. N. (2018). The relationship between family communication patterns and the self-efficacy of student-athletes. *Communication & Sport*, 6(3), 368-389.
- Freeman, P., & Rees, T. (2010). Perceived social support from teammates: Direct and stress-buffering effects on self-confidence. *European Journal of Sport Science*, 10(1), 59–67.
- Furusa, M. G., Knight, C. J., & Hill, D. M. (2021). Parental involvement and children’s enjoyment in sport. *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 13(6), 936-954.
- Gpesser, A. A., & Rodríguez, A. G.M. (2021). Burnout, positivity and passion in young mexican athletes: The mediating effect of social support. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4), 1-14.
- Knight, C. J., Harwood, C. G., & Sellars, P. A. (2016). Supporting adolescent athletes: The role of parents. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 21, 66–77.
- Laurie, E. T. C., Drcar, S. S. J., & Song, X. (2020). Predominant coaching leadership behaviors of high school head basketball coaches: A pilot study. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(11), 219-243.
- Lundy, G., Allan, V., Cowburn, I., &Côté, J. (2019). Parental support, sibling influences, and family dynamics across the development of Canadian interuniversity student-athletes. *Journal of Athlete Development and Experience*, 1(2), 11-23.
- Neyroud, M. C., & Newman, C. J. (2021).Parents’ perspectives on adaptive sports in children with profound intellectual and multiple disabilities. *Children*, 8(9), 23-33.
- Rees, T., & Hardy, L. (2000). An investigation of the social support experiences of high-level sports performers. *The Sport Psychologist*, 14(4), 327–347.
- Stanger, N., Backhouse, S. H., Jennings, A., & McKenna, J. (2018). Linking motivational climate with moral behavior in youth sport: The role of social support, perspective taking, and moral disengagement. *Sport, Exercise, and Performance Psychology*, 7(4), 392.
- Tingaz, E. O. (2020). The psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic on elite athletes, management strategies and post pandemic performance expectations: A semi structured interview study. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 15(7), 73-81.
- Tóth, B. T., Bódi, R., Bodolai, B., Ónadi, Z., Kohut, Z., & Kovács, K. E. (2026). The Role of Social Support and Perfectionist Climate in the Development of Sports Persistence. *Behavioral Sciences*, 16(2), 183.
- Wylleman, P., & Lavallee, D. (2004). A developmental perspective on transitions faced by athletes. *Developmental Sport Psychology*, 507–527.